

Summary: Licensing Best Practices for Sharing Scientific Data

Creative Commons offers recommendations for opening data that organizations produce, collect, publish, and/or host to be publicly shared for scientific inquiry. We aim to ensure that open data is simple to access and use, and to provide guidance that maximizes access, sharing, and reuse of open data. Open data is generally defined as openly accessible, editable, and shareable by anyone for any purpose, and generally licensed under an open license. An open license is a copyright agreement that grants permission to access, reuse, and redistribute the creator's work with few or no restrictions.

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Recommended Legal & Licensing Terms for Sharing Scientific Data

Option A

Creative Commons CCO Public Domain Dedication with Attribution Request

Example attribution statement:

This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CCO 1.0. Attribution is requested. To view a copy of this dedication, visit

<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0>.

CCO is not a license; it is a dedication of the data to the worldwide public domain. Public domain dedication waives copyright and database rights in most jurisdictions around the world. CCO with Attribution Request signals the importance of giving credit through attribution when using data, even though attribution is not legally required for works in the public domain.

Attributions must include four TASL components:

Title of the work, the Author's name, the Source link to the original work (e.g., DOI, PID, website url), and License link.

Option B

Creative Commons CC BY Attribution 4.0 International License

Example attribution statement:

This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

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Attribution is a legal requirement of all CC licenses.

Recommended Metadata Values for Sharing Scientific Data

Metadata should include six TASLAR values: The four TASL attribution components (Title, Author, Source link, and License link) plus Attribution Statement and Rights Statement.

Metadata Value Label	Example Value
<p>Title The title of this work is _____.</p>	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003
<p>Author Please list us as the author.</p>	Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA)
<p>Source link The source for this data is (URL or doi:XXXXXXXX/XXXXXXXXXXXXX).</p>	doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain
<p>License link The license link for this data is (URL).</p>	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
<p>Attribution statement A copy-pasteable concatenation of TASL that can be used to cite us and our sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ours: Title, Author, Source, License</i> • <i>Sources: Title, Author, Source, License</i> 	Korean Land and Water Levels 2003, Korea Meteorological Administration (KMA), doi:XXXXXXXX/kma.domain, http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0
<p>Rights statement Here is a statement that provides a summary of the licensing rights and legal terms for this data.</p>	CCO with Attribution Request. This work is dedicated to the public domain, marked by CCO 1.0, which allows users worldwide to distribute, combine, reanalyze, and build upon the material in any medium or format, with no legal conditions on reuse. Attribution is requested in a standard format to allow reusers to include this information easily.

Using data?

TASL for data attributions

- Title
- Author
- Source link
- License link

Eg., "Suggested attribution:
This Open Data Report by
Jan Ainali. Licensed by [CC
BY 4.0](#).

Sharing data?

TASLAR for metadata values

- Title
- Author
- Source link
- License link
- Attribution statement
- Rights description

"I will include TASLAR in the metadata of this data taht I am sharing, so users know their reuse rights and attribute it."

